

Appendix 3 Task Force DEI Logic Model Materials

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Table 1. Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion Logic Model

Objective: Develop a framework to support workforce diversity, exposure to informatics and awareness of AMIA that enables recruitment and retention efforts of students, faculty, & professionals

Recruitment and Retention				
Strategic Planning Recommendations	Activities	Outputs	Outcomes	Metrics
Create an AMIA that houses research interests related to DEI and diverse informaticians	Promote and seek out researchers from marginalized and historically excluded communities	Research papers, presentations, posters, etc. that are from diverse authors	Increased authors from marginalized and historically excluded in JAMIA and AMIA symposium	First AND accepted papers, presentations and posters
				Last author for submitted AND accepted papers, presentations and posters
				Overall authors for submitted AND accepted papers, presentations and posters
Create an AMIA that houses research interests related to DEI and diverse informaticians	Promote research topics impactful for the health of and important to marginalized communities	Research papers, presentations, posters, etc. that focus on marginalized community health.	Increased representation of topics important to marginalized communities in JAMIA and AMIA symposium	Number of submissions and publications, presentations, posters on health topics impactful for marginalized communities
Create an AMIA that houses research interests related to DEI and diverse informaticians	Promote importance of diversity work	Conference events and e-news that promote DEI work by individuals and groups.	Increased perceived importance of DEI work by AMIA members	Number of e-news articles
				Number of recognition awards at AMIA
Create an AMIA that houses research interests related to DEI and diverse informaticians	Promote member-produced content by members from marginalized and historically excluded communities in e-news that is not strictly academic work	E-news stories which focus on member-produced produced content	Increased representation of work by members from marginalized and historically excluded communities in e-news and AMIA events.	Number of e-news articles and social media posts
Focus on intentional leadership diversity	Mentorship program with a focus on marginalized and historically excluded members	Mentorship program developed	Increased number of AMIA members from marginalized and historically excluded communities with mentors through AMIA	Number of potential mentors from marginalized and historically excluded communities
				Number of mentees from marginalized and historically excluded communities matched with a mentor
Focus on intentional leadership diversity	Leadership programs with a focus on marginalized and historically excluded members	Leadership program developed	Increased leader from marginalized and historically excluded communities at all levels of AMIA	Representation on committees and TFs, WGs, student editorial board.
Fortify existing and creating new outreach programs with broader scopes and partnerships	Targeted outreach and communications to HBCUs, TCUs and HSIs. Outreach can look like invited talks, invited publications, information about upcoming special issues, AMIA deadlines, etc.	Continual communication with these institutions on upcoming conferences, research, calls for research and opportunities	Increased participation in AMIA from these institutions	Number of HBCUs, TCUs and HSIs reached out to each month.

Recruitment and Retention Cont.

Strategic Planning Recommendations	Activities	Outputs	Outcomes	Metrics
Fortify existing and creating new outreach programs with broader scopes and partnerships	Expand HS scholars program to undergraduate institutions with a focus on HBCUs, TCUs, and HSIs and provide opportunities to join AMIA	A new scholars program geared towards HS and undergraduates with structured pathways into AMIA	Improved pathways to informatics for undergraduates and community college students	The number of undergraduates and community college students in an expanded HS scholars program
Fortify existing and creating new outreach programs with broader scopes and partnerships	Partner with BMI departments DEI efforts (creating AMIA membership/attendance waivers and slots for papers, presentations and posters from students in these DEI programs). Also, partnerships to understand approaches to DEI within the AMIA community	Partnerships with BMI departments that support DEI efforts	Support for BMI department's DEI efforts	Number of conference attendees, papers, presentations and posters from these institutions.
Fortify existing and creating new outreach programs with broader scopes and partnerships	Partnership and outreach to organizations that serve marginalized and historically excluded groups (e.g., Black girls Code, Trans Tech Social Enterprises, SNMA, and minority health organizations)	Partnerships that promote these organizations as well as inform their members of AMIA programming and research	Increased representation of these programs at AMIA, and vice versa. Increased communication similar to TCU, HBCU and HSI communication plans.	Number of these programs at AMIA booths
Fortify existing and creating new outreach programs with broader scopes and partnerships	Support and provide venues to other overlooked informatics topics (e.g., public health informatics)	Calls for research on these topics in JAMIA and AMIA symposium	Increased presence of overlooked informatics topics in JAMIA and at AMIA	Number of calls and target outreach within these informatics fields
Diversity in programming, events and conferences	Activities and events promoting collaboration and networking for members from diverse backgrounds with opportunities to access careers and graduate programs	AMIA Conference activities and events	Stronger communities within AMIA which have been traditionally marginalized and historically excluded	Attendance at these activities and events

Support Workforce Diversity				
Strategic Planning Recommendations	Activities	Outputs	Outcomes	Metrics
Reconceptualize working groups	Support every AMIA working group to have a DE&I plan with SMART goals and objectives that are reviewed by the DE&I Sub-Committee.	Working groups with DEI plans and SMART goals/objectives	Increased diversity of WG membership across the board	Percent of WGs in compliance (updated annually)
Collect and share more precise, transparent data on the diversity of AMIA membership, papers, presentations and posters.	Collect and share more precise/transparent data on the diversity of AMIA membership, papers, presentations and posters.	Data on diversity in AMIA	Targeted DEI actions by AMIA through knowledge of how well different groups are represented	Annual reports on the diversity of AMIA membership, papers, presentations and posters and overall changes from previous years
Autonomy and empowerment to allow members to define programming and offerings they need and provide members with an ongoing voice in the organization's strategies.	Listening sessions to understand membership turnover in marginalized and historically excluded communities	Data on member turnover in AMIA, especially within marginalized and historically excluded communities	Targeted DEI actions by AMIA through knowledge of AMIA members' reasons for joining/staying/leaving	The presence of listening sessions conducted every 5 years
Autonomy and empowerment to allow members to define programming and offerings they need and provide members with an ongoing voice in the organization's strategies.	Surveys with members and non-members alike to understand how AMIA is perceived in marginalized and historically excluded communities. Surveys should be assessed and formed by the DEI committee. These should be at all targeted/outreach events, and other, non-DEI focuses, events where AMIA/informatics has a presence.	Data on perception of AMIA within marginalized and historically excluded communities	Targeted DEI actions by AMIA through knowledge of AMIA members' reasons for joining/staying/leaving	The presence of annual surveys overall and at targeted/outreach events.
Autonomy and empowerment to allow members to define programming and offerings they need and provide members with an ongoing voice in the organization's strategies.	Iteratively re-evaluate the logic model, activities, outcomes, and metrics to match realistic goals with temporal and financial constraints	Improved and streamlined logic model	A cohesive plan to address pathways into informatics and DEI in AMIA	A task force committed to refining the logic model
Autonomy and empowerment to allow members to define programming and offerings they need and provide members with an ongoing voice in the organization's strategies.	Define baselines of all metrics in the logic model framework before enacting activities.	Methods to extract metrics, measure baselines and any changes going forward	The ability to track changes in diversity within different aspects of AMIA	The ability to measure each metric for the recommended actions
A formal subcommittee under the DEI Committee to further examine systemic racism and health equity and	A formal subcommittee under the DEI Committee to further examine systemic racism and health equity and	A subcommittee to examine systemic racism and health equity	Identified opportunities for AMIA to address systemic racism and health equity using its status in the field	The presence of a formal subcommittee

determine if/where AMIA can lead	determine if/where AMIA can lead			
Support Workforce Diversity Cont.				
Strategic Planning Recommendations	Activities	Outputs	Outcomes	Metrics
Recruitment and retainment of executive DEI AMIA staff member	Create a full-time position who is responsible for all AMIA DEI oversight.	A full-time position for a DEI officer	Accountability check ins from AMIA leadership to the DEI officer	The presence of a full-time position

Exposure to Informatics				
Strategic Planning Recommendations	Activities	Outputs	Outcomes	Metrics
Begin feasibility and business planning to introduce large number of lower-cost virtual conferences	Begin feasibility and business planning to introduce large number of lower-cost virtual conferences that do not sacrifice quality.	Plans on how to introduce low-cost virtual conferences	Low-cost virtual conferences and increased diversity in attendees compared to in-person AMIA	The number of low-cost virtual conference options (hybrid or otherwise) and attendance by individuals from marginalized and historically excluded communities.
Fortify existing and creating new outreach programs with broader scopes and partnerships	Design mechanisms for current members to serve as liaisons to conferences that serve marginalized and historically excluded communities in STEM.	Liaison funding and information for individuals	AMIA members with financial and logistical support to serve as liaisons at conferences which serve marginalized and historically excluded communities	Number of liaisons supported
Fortify existing and creating new outreach programs with broader scopes and partnerships	Develop AMIA's role as a communicator between academia/industry and the broader community	Methods, programs and partnerships to disperse research knowledge about health equity	Relationships with marginalized and historically excluded communities focused around healthcare topics	Number of partnerships with communities to disperse knowledge

7 DEI Initiatives in Similar Associations Related to: (1) Workforce Diversity; (2) Exposure; and (3) Recruitment and Retention

Activity	American Medical Informatics Association (AMIA)	American Economics Association (AEA)	AcademyHealth	Association of American Medical Colleges (AAMC)	American Psychological Association (APA)	Academy of Management (AOM)
Scholarly research						
Diverse representation among conference, panel, seminars, and other forums		X	X	X	X	X
Code of conduct and expectations for conferences, seminars, and panels to create inclusive spaces for productive conversation		X			X	X
Diverse and inclusive standards for journals that reduce editorial biases		X	X		X	
Collegiality						
"Good Samaritan" ethic to promote a willingness to listen and speak up on behalf of marginalized or historically excluded groups experiencing discrimination or inappropriate behavior		X		X		
Environment facilitates support for working with junior colleagues, students, trainees regardless of background		X	X	X	X	X
Creates environment to support all academic, personal, and professional goals			X	X	X	X

Provide process to respond to cases of exclusion, discrimination, inappropriate behavior, harassment, and unwelcome treatment		X		X		
Improving the pipeline						
Process to share professional and academic opportunities for students and trainees regardless of background		X	X		X	X
Provide support and curricula that engages students and trainees from all backgrounds		X		X	X	
Utilizes evidence-based and inclusive pedagogy		X				
Improve message of inclusion for non-traditional and marginalized or historically excluded students and trainees		X		X		X